

Oxidation of Hydrazine by Nitrous Acid—Part III

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The oxidation of hydrazine with nitrous acid proceeds along simultaneous one and two equivalent processes to a host of nitrogen products in various oxidation states. With nitrite being added to hydrazine the products are mainly N_3H , NH_5 and N_2 , while in the reverse case the HNO_2 is reduced successively to hyponitrous acid ($H_2N_2O_2$) and ultimately to nitrogen.

THE tendency of the reduction of HNO_2 to lower oxidation states of nitrogen can be determined by the following oxidation potentials given by Latimer¹.

With respect to oxidation of hydrazine, nitrous acid has been shown to behave as both one and two equivalent oxidants followed by reaction (iv), (v) or (vi)

Earlier workers²⁻⁷ had studied the reaction of hydrazine and nitrous acid and proposed hydrazoic acid. Browne and Wilcoxon⁸ also pointed out that hydrazoic acid might also be derivable from some mixed ammonia hydrazine derivative of nitrous acid such as isotetrazene and tetrazene. Angeli⁹ and others¹⁰⁻¹⁷ obtained hydrazoic acid by action of the salts of nitrous acid on hydrazine but no reference could be found regarding the stoichiometric behaviour of nitrous acid towards hydrazine.

In the present work we have shown the exact course of events in the reaction between them, potentiometrically.

Experimental

By weighing the exact amount from formula weight of sodium nitrite (B.D.H.) the stock solution of $M/10$ was prepared in air-free redistilled water and was standardised by standard $KMnO_4$ solution¹⁸. The stock solution of $M/10$ hydrazine sulphate

(B.D.H.) was also prepared in the same way and standardised by iodate method¹⁹. The other experimental potentiometric methods were adopted as reported by Prasad and Ojha²⁰.

TABLE 1. 0.091M SODIUM NITRITE ADDED IN 10 ML. OF 0.00931M HYDRAZINE SULPHATE SOLUTION

Sl. No.	Acid conc. H_2SO_4 (approx.)	Temp./period of storage	Point of inflexion (in ml.)	Molar ratio
1.	0.02N	30°/24 hr	1.5	1.5 moles of $NaNO_2$ per mole of hydrazine.
2.	1N	"	1.5	"
3.	2N	"	1.5	"
4.	4N	"	1.5	"
5.	8N	"	1.5	"
6.	18N	60°/24 hr	1.5	"

TABLE 2. 0.0931M HYDRAZINE ADDED TO 10 ML. OF 0.0091M $NaNO_2$ SOLUTION

Sl. No.	Acid conc. H_2SO_4 (approx.)	Temp./period of storage	Point of inflexion (in ml.)	Molar ratio
1.	0.1N	30°/24 hr	0.6, 1.45	0.619 and 1.505 moles of hydrazine per mole of $NaNO_2$.
2.	1N	"	0.6, 1.45	"
3.	2N	"	0.6	0.619 mole of hydrazine per mole of $NaNO_2$.
4.	4N	"	0.6	"
5.	8N	"	0.6	"

Results and Discussion

Under all conditions, when sodium nitrite is added to hydrazine, an inflexion appears at 1.5 moles of the former per mole of the latter according to the one and two equivalent redox reactions through (i) and (ii).

The results can however be explained only in terms of one electron reduction of nitrous acid (i) and a simultaneous one and two equivalent oxidations of hydrazine as given in (iv) and (vi). This is supported

by the fact that effervescence due to nitrogen evolution does take place and the reaction mixture gives

Fig. 1. Cell : 10 mls of 0.00931M Hydrazine solution. [Y-axis and been shifted 10 Divn. successively towards the right].

tests on NH_3 by Nessler's reagent. The overall reaction is

In the reverse case, *i.e.*, when hydrazine is added to nitrous acid, partial destruction of it by self decomposition can not be prevented and an inflexion always appears at 0.62 mole, rather than 0.66 moles, hydrazine per mole nitrous acid. If this partial destruction is assumed to be due to disproportionation of nitrous acid,

it is possible to explain this result in terms of the scheme given above, *i.e.*, (viii). But in a few cases (acid concentration $< 2N$ H_2SO_4 medium) a second inflexion also appears at 1.5 moles of hydrazine (Fig. 2). This indicates that the above scheme is not operative at high acidities and this can be explained in terms of two equivalent oxidation of hydrazine through (v) and (vi) simultaneously and successive reduction of nitrous acid to hyponitrous acid and ultimately to nitrogen.

The reduction of hyponitrous acid to nitrogen is more easily effected through a complementary one equivalent oxidation of hydrazine.

Fig. 2. Cell : 10 mls of 0.0091M Sod. Nitrite solution. [Y-axis has been shifted by 20 Divn. successively for 4 and 5 towards the right].

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